

The Inconsistence of Academic Qualifications, Years' of Experience and Position for Forensic Investigations Job Opportunities in the Public Sector: A Case Study of South Africa

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ABSTRACT

The National Development Plan (NDP) (2030) refers to the professionalisation of public service in South Africa. In support of the NDP, the National Framework towards Professionalisation of Public Sector was developed to address the current challenges of unethical, incompetence and unprofessionalism of public servants as it hinders service delivery and the effectiveness of South Africa as a developmental state. For South Africa to achieve its developmental goal, it is necessary to professionalise the public service sector. This article explores the inconsistency of academic qualifications, years of experience, and positions for forensic investigations careers in South Africa's public sector. The article focuses on successful candidates to be appointed as forensic/ fraud investigators and to check if the normal recruitment process has been followed. The study adopted a qualitative research approach to gather and analyse data. The researcher utilised various job adverts from different government institutions related to forensic investigations and anti-corruption vacancies in this study. The study established that as part of the government's effort to professionalise public service, an advert with preferred requirements for the post will be published, followed by a shortlist of qualified applicants and interviews with the candidates. The study found inconsistencies regarding academic qualifications and years of experience required when positions of forensic investigations are advertised in South Africa's public sector.

Keywords: Bachelor, forensic investigators, forensic investigations, qualifications, vacancies.

INTRODUCTION

To professionalise public service requires the South African government to embark on a thorough recruitment drive process that seeks to employ public servants (both experienced and new entrants) who are ethical, professional, and capable enough to deliver the basic needs (services) to ordinary citizens. The professionalization of the public service is deemed necessary to advance the NDP agenda of a developmental state (The National School of Government, 2022:29). South African history is not different to most countries such as Brazil, Denmark, Mozambique, Norway, Turkey and Zimbabwe to mention the few which are characterised by incompetent, unprofessionalism and unethical conduct by members of the executives and public servants (The National School of Government, 2020:71). The inability and failure of the state to render basic services such as water, roads, housing and electricity to the communities is linked to the rising number of service delivery protests as well as dilapidated infrastructure such as roads and railway. There is no doubt that service delivery is on the brink of collapse (incompletely disarray) in South Africa due to, amongst other things, the failure of recruitment processes, which brought public servants who are unethical and unfit to execute their duties. These challenges are mainly found across the spheres of government in South Africa. As part of addressing the professionalisation of the public service and the failures of the South African government to render basic services, criteria are set for applicants who want to become public servants when public vacancies are advertised. Amongst the criteria set in the adverts is the number of years of experience, including appropriate or relevant qualification(s) in the field of the advertised vacancies. As a result, this article is primarily focused on the inconsistency of academic qualifications, years of experience and positions for forensic investigations job opportunities in the public sector of South Africa.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND DESIGN

The research methodology was employed to formulate the research topic and present study results based on the data from universities and state institutions. Creswell and Poth (2016) defined research design as the whole study process whereby the researcher conceptualises a research problem, formulates research questions, collects data, analyses, interprets, and writes the report. Moreover, Sileyew (2019) emphasise that the purpose of research design is to provide a proper guide to the study. However, the research design is comprised of two dominant approaches, which are qualitative and quantitative. However, this study adopted a qualitative approach to gather and analyse data.

Qualitative research design is typically flexible (meaning the study topic and objectives can change quickly based on emerging data and allows the researcher to adapt to newly collected data which require more examination) and subjective in that the study results are based on the participants' views, feelings and experience about the study topic (Haven & Van Grootel, 2019). This study aims to align academic qualifications and years of experience for forensic/ fraud investigations and anti-fraud and corruption vacancies graded and evaluated on the same level by the Department of Public Service and Administration (DPSA) in the public sector of South Africa. As a result, the researcher deemed a qualitative research design appropriate to highlight the

inconsistency of the qualifications, years of experience, and positions for forensic investigations career opportunities within South African state institutions.

Given the nature and structure of this study, the researcher utilised the secondary data gathered from universities' websites and published prospectus and vacancies published by DPSA, including other state institutions. The presented data was selected purposively to address the study topic. The researcher followed purposive sampling to highlight the relevant qualifications for forensic/fraud investigations and anti-fraud and corruption careers by presenting selected academic qualifications and criteria set when these vacancies are advertised (Bakkalbasioglu, 2020:689). The data was analysed using Textual and Thematic Content Analysis (TCA). This is because scholars' most commonly used data for content analysis is textual (transcribed text), which is connected to themes (Stemler, 2015:2).

Thus, TCA was used to define and interpret the collected data from South African universities (data published from universities' websites and prospectus), DPSA and other state institutions (published vacancies), including to select codes and construct themes to highlight the inconsistency of academic qualifications, years of experience and position for forensic investigations job opportunities in the public sector of South Africa (Kiger & Varpio, 2020:2).

THEORETICAL DISCUSSION AND PRESENTATION OF THEMES

The study began by providing a background summary regarding the correlation between forensic investigations and anti-fraud and corruption vacancies. In South Africa, some state departments and institutions use these vacancies interchangeably. Individuals may sometimes be employed within the anti-fraud and corruption unit to conduct forensic investigations rather than conduct fraud risk assessments and awareness. Similarly, individuals may be employed within the forensic investigation unit but not perform forensic investigations duties while executing fraud risk assessments or fraud awareness duties, which are usually connected to anti-fraud and corruption, as well as ethics management units. The recruited or employed individuals are also circulated amongst the forensic investigations and anti-corruption units within the public sector of South Africa. The assertion above confirms that personnel are also utilised interchangeably within forensic investigations, anti-fraud and corruption, and ethics management. Forensic investigations, anti-fraud and corruption, and ethics management vacancies share the same qualifications and requirements when advertised.

The study was informed by the lack of consistency of academic qualifications, years of experience and positions in forensic investigations careers in the public sector of South Africa. The inconsistency was despite the fact that the DPSA regulates the public sector of South Africa as a single administration department. According to the Public Service Act of 1994, the Minister responsible for the DPSA is required to, amongst other roles, set up the norms and standards regarding "the functions of the public service, organisational structures, establishments of departments and other organisational and governance arrangements in the public service." Furthermore, public service jobs are graded, evaluated and approved by the DPSA.

FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS-RELATED QUALIFICATIONS OFFERED BY SOUTH AFRICAN UNIVERSITIES

The University of North West (NWU) offers courses in Bachelor of Arts (BA) in Public Governance with Policing Practice with possible careers as Public Administrator, Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice Officer and Field Investigation Officer, and Bachelor of Commerce (BCom) in Law with possible careers as Commercial Sector and Legal Advisor; and Bachelors of Laws (*thereafter abbreviated and/ or commonly known or some people refer to as LLB*) with possible careers as Attorney, Advocate, State Prosecutor, Magistrate, Commercial Sector and Legal Advisor (NWU, 2023).

In terms of the University of South Africa (UNISA) registration and curriculum information for Bachelor of Arts in Police Science, Bachelor of Arts in Forensic Science and Technology and Postgraduate Diploma in Forensic Auditing, students who enrolled and completed these three (3) qualifications studied amongst other modules the "Investigative Principles for Policing I – III, Forensic Methods and Techniques, Investigation of Selected Crimes and Transgressions, Information Gatherings, Principles of Evidence in Forensic Investigations, Forensic Crime Intelligence, Forensic Investigative Resources, Criminal Justice Research Methodology, Law of Evidence and Criminal Procedure; and Applied Law for Forensic Auditors, Applied Labour Law for Forensic Auditors, Forensic Audit Reporting, Financial Fraud Schemes, Fraud Prevention and Detection and Fraud Investigation for Forensic Auditors" as modules (UNISA, 2023).

According to the University of KwaZulu-Natal (UKZN) 2023 Postgraduate Prospectus, the university offers Postgraduate Diplomas in Forensic Investigations and Criminal Justice with investigation modules, namely Forensic Investigative Accounting, Forensic Investigation Techniques and Forensic Reporting (UKZN, 2023). This further translates that graduates who completed these modules and qualifications meet the minimum requirements of being Criminal Investigators, Crime Intelligence Personnel, Detectives, Investigators, Environmental Officers, Criminal Investigations Ethics and Integrity Management Officers, Forensic Investigators, Forensic Consultants: Forensic Investigations, Forensic Auditors; Fraud Investigators; Fraud and Anti-Corruption Officers; Fraud Prevention and Ethics Managements Officers, Investigations and Loss Control Personnel; Operational and Compliance Officers; Integrity and Investigation Officers; Law Administration, Compliance, Monitoring, Prevention and Analysis Personnel; Traffic Law Administrators; Criminal Justice System Oversight Personnel (Law Enforcement); Security Investigations and Counter Measure Personnel; Special Investigators and any related field as those graduates acquire theoretical investigation background or knowledge.

Moreover, the UKZN (2023) emphasises that the Postgraduate Diplomas in Forensic Investigations and Criminal Justice "provides working professionals (not necessarily accountants or lawyers) with the knowledge and skills necessary to specialise in the field of forensic investigative auditing – a specialised branch of forensic investigation, which uses intelligence gathering techniques, together with accounting, legal and communication skills, to investigate and provide evidence of crimes of a financial or commercial nature."

With regard to the 2023 University of Limpopo (UL) prospectus, the university offers a Bachelor of Arts (Criminology and Psychology stream). The course comprises modules amongst criminologists, crime scene experts and private investigators (UL, 2023:1). The Tshwane University of Technology

(TUT) offers an Advanced Diploma in Policing whereby a Crime Investigation listed as a compulsory module to be studied by a registered order to complete the degree (TUT, 2023). As a result, individuals or graduates who completed these modules, courses and qualifications can qualify to be Criminal Investigators, Crime Intelligence Personnel Criminologists, Detectives, Ethics and Integrity Management Officers; Investigators, Forensic Investigators, Fraud Investigators, Fraud and Anti-Corruption Officers, Fraud Prevention Personnel, Investigations and Loss Control Officers; Environmental Officers: Criminal Investigations; Integrity and Investigation Officers; Law Administration, Compliance, Monitoring, Prevention and Analysis Personnel; Traffic Law Administrators; Criminal Justice System Oversight Personnel (Law Enforcement); Security Investigations and Counter Measure Personnel; Special Investigators and any related field as such individual acquired theoretical knowledge on criminology and crime investigation.

Over and above, the university emphasises that the crime investigation module aims to empower students with academic knowledge "to conduct successful investigations relating to organised crime that require proactive approaches, which are generally based on criminal intelligence analysis. The students will also be able to determine whether the intelligence gathering and analysis results can be connected to the criminal conduct of groups or networks" (TUT, 2023).

The University of Pretoria (UP) offers courses in Postgraduate Diploma in Investigation and Forensic Accounting and Master of Philosophy in Fraud Risk Management (thereafter referred to as *MPhil in Fraud Risk Management*). The qualifications provide investigation techniques for various economic crimes through modules namely "Economic Crime Schemes, Fraud Risk Management, Investigation of Financial Crime, Law for Commercial Forensic Practitioners, Money Laundering Detection & Investigation, Investigation of Civil Disputes, Investigation and Management of Cyber & Electronic Crime, Interviewing Skills for Fraud Examiners and Auditors, Prevention & Detection of Corruption & Procurement Fraud and Basic Financial Investigation" (UP, 2018:17).

According to UP (2018:4), the courses were developed by the Forensic Accounting Unit in the Department of Auditing at UP to warrant institutions to "detect, investigate, prevent and to manage the risks of fraud and corruption." In addition, those who complete these courses will be able to "manage the risks of criminal and civil sanctions for non-compliance as well as the reputational risk associated with perceived or actual non-compliance" in their respective institutions.

Moreover, these courses can be enrolled by forensic investigators, commercial crime investigators and prosecutors, fraud examiners, compliance officers, financial and risk managers, company secretaries, attorneys, auditors, accountants and business consultants, procurement officials, insurance claims assessors, detectives, and investigators attached to the South African Police Service (SAPS) as well as other law enforcement agencies who have extensive experience in the field of forensic investigations including individuals who holding relevant forensic/fraud investigations qualifications encourage to apply for admission and enrolments (UP, 2018:8-14).

The University of Venda (UNIVEN) offers a Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice as a qualification (UNIVEN, 2023), while the University of Johannesburg (UJ) offers a Higher Certificate in Criminal Justice and Forensic Investigations (UJ, 2022). In terms of the Vaal University of Technology (VUT) 2023 Human Science Prospectus, the university offers a Diploma and Advanced Diploma in Policing with modules such as Investigation of Crime I – IV, Electronic Information and Communication Law, Prevention and Combating of Corrupt Activities and Road Traffic Accident Investigation. It was pointed out that the course is designed to equip students with theory as well as best practices for investigations and leadership terms, concepts, and principles as well as for

such students to able to act professionally, including making ethical decisions while executing their official's duties (VUT, 2023:56-57).

According to Walter Sisulu University (WSU) Undergraduate Academic Programme, the university offers a Bachelor of Laws and a Bachelor of Social Science (Criminology). It was further expressed that individuals who completed a Bachelor of Laws and Bachelor of Social Science (Criminology) can seek opportunities in the Correctional Services, Justice and Policing field, including but not limited to self-employment as a Consultant within the Investigations field (WSU, 2005 - 2021).

Thus, individuals who completed Higher Certificate in Criminal Justice and Forensic Investigations, Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice, Bachelor of Laws and Bachelor of Social Science (Criminology), Postgraduate Diploma in Investigation and Forensic Accounting, and Master of Philosophy in Fraud Risk Management can qualify as Criminal Investigators; Crime Intelligence; Cybercrime Investigators; Detectives; Digital Forensic Investigators; Investigators; Forensic Investigators; Forensic Consultants: Forensic Investigations; Forensic Auditors; Fraud Investigators; Fraud and Anti-Corruption Officers; Fraud Prevention Officers; Investigations and Loss Control Investigators/ Officers; Environmental Officers: Criminal Investigations; Operational and Compliance Officers; Law Administration, Compliance, Monitoring, Prevention and Analysis Officers; Traffic Law Administrators; Criminal Justice System Oversight Personnel (Law Enforcement); Security Investigations and Counter Measure Personnel; Special Investigators; Ethics and Integrity Management Officers and any related field.

The researcher is of the view that qualifications such as Advanced or National Diploma in Policing, Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice, Bachelor of Arts (Criminology and Psychology stream), Bachelor of Arts in Police Science, Bachelor of Arts (BA) in Public Governance with Policing Practice, Bachelor of Arts in Forensic Science and Technology, Bachelor of Laws and Bachelor of Social Science (Criminology), Higher Certificate in Criminal Justice and Forensic Investigations, Bachelor of Law (LLB), Postgraduate Diploma in Investigation and Forensic Accounting, Postgraduate Diploma in Forensic Auditing, Postgraduate Diplomas in Forensic Investigations and Criminal Justice and MPhil in Fraud Risk Management need to be listed as relevant qualifications when detectives, investigators, Anti-Fraud and Corruption and forensic/ fraud investigations vacancies advertised. Moreover, the researcher believes that candidates who obtained these listed qualifications must be prioritised during the shortlisting processes, allowing them to compete for these vacancies.

DIFFERENT JOB ADVERT FOR FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS AND ANTI-FRAUD AND CORRUPTION VACANCIES

Consequently, the analysis and discussion of Forensic Auditor/ Investigations, Fraud Prevention and Anti-Fraud and Corruption vacancies published by different government departments, institutions and municipalities were captured in the diagrams below and discussed briefly thereafter:

Table 1. Senior Investigations Positions (Heads & Managers)

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	City of Tshwane
Post/ Position	DIVISIONAL HEAD: ETHICS MANAGEMENT AND FORENSIC SERVICES

Requirements	✓ Applicants must hold a Bachelor's Degree in Forensic Accounting, Forensic Investigation, Internal Audit or any other related field of study to the advertised post/ position. Certified Fraud Examiners (CFE) applicants will be in a better position (stand a chance) than other applicants. Applicants must have a proven track record and 10 years of vast experience in forensic audit, investigations, and fraud prevention.
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[Source: **City of Tshwane**, Internal/ External Job Forum 3/ 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Home Affairs
Post/ Position	CHIEF DIRECTOR: PREVENTION AND ANALYSIS
Requirements	✓ Candidates must hold an undergraduate academic qualification (NQF level 7) in Criminal Justice, Criminology, Forensic Investigation, Intelligence Management, Law or related field, Police Administration and Management as recognised by the South African Qualification Authority (SAQA). Candidates must have five (5) years of experience at a Senior Managerial level in a related field, a vast experience in Crime Analysis and Prevention, and a pre-entry Senior Management Services Certificate, which the National School of Government endorses.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 14 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Planning, Monitoring and Evaluation
Post/ Position	SENIOR EXPERT ON ANTI-CORRUPTION, MONITORING AND EVALUATION
Requirements	✓ "A 3-year tertiary qualification (NQF level 7) in Public Administration/ Social Sciences/ Law or related field of study. A postgraduate qualification (NQF level 8 or higher) will be an added advantage. Minimum of 10 years appropriate experience in public sector governance or civil society and/or government anti-corruption sector, criminal justice system, or forensic auditing (public procurement/supply chain management) with at least 5 years proven experience as a member of the Senior Management Service (SMS) in the Public Service or equivalent."

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 30 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	National Lotteries Commission (NLC),
Post/ Position	HEAD: FORENSIC INVESTIGATION & QUALITY ASSURANCE
Requirements	✓ Candidates must hold a postgraduate degree (NQF level 8) in accounting, auditing, forensic auditing, and law. Candidates must also have a CFE or Certified Fraud Practitioner (CFP) membership. Candidates must have 10 years of working experience, of which a

	minimum of five (5) years of experience must be at the supervision (managerial) level.
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[Source: **The National Lotteries Commission (NLC)**, Vacancies]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Armaments Corporation of South Africa (ARMSCOR)
Post/ Position	MANAGER: FORENSIC & SPECIALISED INVESTIGATIONS (FSI)
Requirements	✓ Candidates are required to have a B. Com Degree in Auditing or Investigation, or a related Degree or B-Tech, plus an Honours Degree or Postgraduate Diploma Qualification. Holding a CIA/ CFE/ CA(SA) or any related Audit/ Investigation/ Governance Certificate will serve as an added advantage. Candidates must have at least seven (7) years of post-article audit experience and a minimum of three (3) years of solid managerial experience in the management of investigations.

[Source: **ARMSCOR**, Vacancy for the Manager: Forensic & Specialised Investigations (FSI) within the Audit Department; 2023]

From the five (5) senior positions advertised by four different state institutions, only three (3) entities require '10 years of working experience, of which three (3) institutions went as far as highlighting that a minimum of five (5) years' experience' within the 10 years should be from the managerial level in fraud prevention, anti-fraud and corruption, and forensic audit and investigations and/ or a related field. The four (4) vacancies to be specific Divisional Head: Ethics Management and Forensic Services, Chief Director: Prevention and Analysis, Senior Expert on Anti-Corruption, Monitoring and Evaluation and Head: Forensic Investigation & Quality Assurance are strategic and senior managerial posts which are closely equivalent to each other including falling within the same mainstream of humanities, law and social sciences.

However, the titles of the positions and qualifications and years of experience requirements of the vacancies are not aligned with each other, despite the fact that these posts were advertised by institutions within the different spheres of government. The most commonly shared requirements are Forensic Auditing/ Investigation, Law and Auditing as qualifications and CFE, despite the fact that all the posts tend to manage investigations. One (1) State-Owned Enterprise AMSCOR set requirements of seven (7) years experience for Manager: Forensic & Specialised Investigations (FSI), of which three (3) years should be at the managerial level in the management of investigations.

The researcher found that in all four vacancies, all the qualifications set as requirements are relevant, but not all presented as requirements in all the vacancies. It appears that each institution set its number of years of experience, including preferred qualifications, despite that vacancies mandate to fight against fraud and corruption in the public sector through conducting fraud prevention and anti-fraud and corruption awareness as well as conducting forensic audits/ investigations when these offences are detected and reported.

Table 2. Medium Management Service (MMS) Positions (Deputy Directors)

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS
Prerequisite	✓ "Applicants must have a Grade 12 Certificate and Degree or National Diploma in Forensic Investigations/ Law/ Auditing / Forensic Accounting/ Police Administration/ Criminal Justice and/ or related field. Minimum of 5 years of credible and applicable experience in the Forensic Investigation field and Project management experience. Membership of the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE) or Institution of Commercial Forensic Practitioners (ICFP) is recommended."

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 14 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Cooperative Governance
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: ANTI-CORRUPTION
Set Criteria	✓ Candidates must have a Matric (Grade 12) Certificate plus a three (3) year National Diploma or Bachelor's degree (NQF level 6 or 7 as acknowledged by SAQA) in Law, Social Science or equivalent qualification. Moreover, a candidate must have three (3) to five (5) years of experience within a related post field.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 45 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Community Safety
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: CRIMINAL JUSTICE SYSTEM OVERSIGHT
Requirements	✓ Candidates must have a Matric and Bachelor's Degree (NQF level 7) in Criminal Justice, Law Enforcement and LLB. Candidates must have three (3) to five (5) years of relevant working experience within the criminal justice system environment, of which three (3) years' experience should be in junior management equivalent to Assistant Director Level.

[Source: **Department of Community Safety**, Nasi iSpani | 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Employment and Labour
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: ANTI-FRAUD AND ANTI-CORRUPTION
Prerequisite	✓ Applicants must have a three (3) year tertiary qualification (NQF level 6) in Commerce, Forensic Accounting, Forensic Audit or Risk Management. In addition, applicants must have five (5) years experience, of which three (3) years experience must be at the

	functional level within the Risk, Fraud and Anti-Corruption field plus two (2) years experience in supervisory (managerial) level.
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[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 27 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of International Relations and Cooperation
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: OPERATIONAL, COMPLIANCE & FORENSIC AUDIT
Criteria set	✓ Candidates must hold NQF level 7 or similar qualification, National Diploma or Bachelor's Degree in Accounting, Forensic Audit or Internal Audit. Candidates must have majored in Auditing or Forensic Auditing subjects when obtaining their qualifications. The candidates must hold a membership or register with the Institute of Internal Auditors of South Africa (IIASA) and CFE. Candidates must have at least five (5) years of experience in forensic investigation.

[Source: **Source: DPSA**, Circular 06 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	National Prosecuting Authority
Post/ Position	SENIOR FINANCIAL INVESTIGATOR
Requirements	✓ Applicants must have a Bachelor's Degree or National Diploma (NQF level 7 or 6) in Criminal Investigation, Forensic Auditing, Forensic Investigations or equivalent qualification. Applicants who are CFE will stand a better chance. Applicants must have at least five (5) years' experience in financial investigation.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 37 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Social Development
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: COMPLIANCE MONITORING AND REPORTING
Prerequisite	✓ Candidates must hold a Bachelor's Degree (NQF level 7) in Social Sciences, Public Administration or equivalent academic qualification and have three (3) years' credible junior managerial experience in non-profit governance. Candidates with qualifications in Compliance Management, Financial Management, Forensic Investigation or Law will be better positioned to compete.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 04 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Sport, Arts and Culture
Post/ Position	DEPUTY DIRECTOR: FRAUD/ FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS
Requirements	✓ Candidates must have at least a minimum qualification of a Bachelor's Degree (NQF level 7) or National Diploma (NQF level 6)

	in Accounting, Auditing, Business Science, Financial Management, Law plus five (5) to seven (7) years practical experience within the investigation environment, of which three (3) years or more experience must be in managerial (supervisory) level. Candidates who have completed relevant Forensic Accounting and Fraud Examination training, possess a CFE Certificate or are affiliated with ACFE stand a better chance.
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[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 03 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Financial Sector Conduct Authority (FSCA)
Post/ Position	FORENSIC INVESTIGATOR: MARKET ABUSE DEPARTMENT
Set Criteria	✓ Applicants must hold a Bachelor's Degree in Commerce or LLB with at least five (5) years' experience in Forensic Accounting, Forensic Investigation, Litigation or Prosecution. Applicants must understand and be knowledgeable of the Law of Evidence about admissibility, computer-generated and documentary evidence, and having experience within the financial sector will be an added advantage.

[Source: **FSCA**, Forensic Investigator: Market Abuse Department; 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Financial Sector Conduct Authority (FSCA)
Post/ Position	INVESTIGATOR X3 : ENFORCEMENT DEPARTMENT
Set prerequisite	✓ Candidates must possess accounting, forensics, and LLB degrees and five (5) years of experience in forensic accounting, investigation, litigation, and prosecution. Candidates must be admitted as attorneys or advocates (for law incumbents). Candidates with a good understanding and knowledge of the Law of Evidence about admissibility, computer-generated and documentary evidence, and financial sector experience will be an added advantage.

[Source: **FSCA**, Investigator X3: Enforcement Department; 2023]

The researcher found that of the 10 vacancies advertised and presented above, the salary levels are more equivalent, including falling within the same mainstream of humanities, law and social sciences. However, the years of experience, the title of the position and the qualifications requirements are not aligned with each other, despite that these vacancies were advertised by eight (8) different government departments accountable and regulated by the DPSA and one (1) SOE accountable to National Treasury as a government department.

Furthermore, the researcher established that the required number of years of work experience is five (5) in the investigations field by five (5) institutions, of which three (3) departments require that an applicant must have a minimum of three (3) years' experience' at junior/ relevant managerial

level. Moreover, three (3) institutions set the requirements of five (5) years of experience in forensic investigation, while one (1) department required financial investigations. One (1) department

required 'three (3) to five (5) years' experience' in anti-corruption related field while the other department required five (5) to seven (7) years "practical investigative experience," of which three (3) years should be from managerial level. Four (4) government departments recommended or set the affiliation to Association/ Certified Fraud Examiner (A/CFE) as an added advantage. These positions were graded and evaluated on the same level but set different qualifications and several years of experience as requirements.

Some of the qualifications listed in some of the vacancies above are modules rather than qualifications; for instance, crime investigation is a module studied as part of the qualification for a Diploma/ Advance Diploma in Policing. Thus, from the listed relevant qualifications for forensic investigations and anti-fraud and corruption above, there is no qualification referred to as Criminal Investigation contrary to the requirement set by the NPA for the position of Senior Financial Investigator. Notwithstanding that, the appointed candidates for most of the listed positions above will be responsible for, amongst other things, conducting and managing forensic investigations and following up on implementing the recommendations emanating from the carried-out forensic investigations.

Table 3. Supervisory Level (Assistant Directors)

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development
Post/ Position	ASSISTANT DIRECTOR: FRAUD PREVENTION AND ETHICS MANAGEMENT
Prerequisite	✓ Interested applicants must have a Grade 12 Certificate and National Diploma or Bachelor's Degree in Criminology, Internal Auditing and Risk Management. Applicants must have at least three (3) years of experience in fraud awareness, prevention, and ethics management, including interrelating at the strategic and operational levels.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 10 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Employment and Labour
Post/ Position	ASSISTANT DIRECTOR: FRAUD PREVENTION
Requirements	✓ Applicants must have a three (3) year tertiary qualification in Commerce, Criminal, Forensic Accounting, Forensic Audit or Risk Management plus four (4) years' practical experience in fraud management.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 01 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Employment and Labour
Post/ Position	ASSISTANT DIRECTOR: ANTI-FRAUD AND CORRUPTION

Set Criteria	✓ Candidates must have a (NQF level 6) National Diploma or (NQF level 7) Bachelor's Degree in Accounting, Auditing, Forensic Investigation and Law. Candidates must have five (5) years of experience within the forensic investigations environment, of which three (3) years must be at the functional and two (2) years at the supervisory level.
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[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 45 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	National Prosecuting Authority
Post/ Position	DATA ANALYST
Prerequisite	✓ Interested applicants must have a Bachelor's Degree or advanced diploma (NQF Level 7) and/ or Baccalaureus Technologiae (B-Tech) in Forensics, Law, Policing and/ or Data and/ or Engineering, Physical Science or equivalent qualification. Applicants must have three (3) years' experience in criminal and/ or forensic investigations.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 25 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Office of the Chief Justice
Post/ Position	ASSISTANT DIRECTOR: FORENSIC AUDITOR
Set Criteria	✓ Applicants interested in applying for this position must have a Matric (Grade 12) Certificate plus three (3) three-year National Diplomas or Bachelor's Degrees in Accounting, Auditing, Criminal or Fraud Investigations, Police Administration or Public Service Administration. Interested applicants must have at least three (3) years of appropriate experience, including in a managerial (supervisory) role within the Forensic Auditing or Investigation field.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 10 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Office of the Premier
Post/ Position	ASSISTANT DIRECTOR: INVESTIGATION
Prerequisite	✓ Candidates must have three (3) years of relevant tertiary qualification (NQF level 6 & 7) or comparable qualification. Candidates must have at least three (3) to five (5) years of experience related to the applicable discipline field, of which two (2) years must be at the supervisory (managerial) level.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 43 of 2021]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Transport
Post/ Position	ASSISTANT DIRECTOR: FORENSIC INVESTIGATIONS

Requirements	✓ Applicants must have a suitable tertiary qualification (NQF level 6) in accounting, auditing, forensic investigations, and law, plus three (3) years of experience as a supervisor or practitioner within the forensic investigations environment. Being a CFE or ICFP is recommended.
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[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 27 of 2023]

From the three (3) Assistant Directors' positions of Anti-Fraud and Corruption presented and analysed above, the researcher established that qualifications and the number of years of experience set are not aligned, including the post/ position being titled differently, despite that the appointed candidates will be performing less the same duties of co-ordinating and implementing anti-fraud and corruption strategy, awareness programmes as well as facilitating the investigations of reported fraud and corruption within the respective Departments. Moreover, there was inconsistency in the number of years of experience required to be appointed to these vacancies, notwithstanding that these posts are graded and evaluated on the same level and advertised by two government departments accountable to the DPSA. In addition, two (2) vacancies were advertised by the Department of Employment and Labour with different criteria about qualifications and years of work experience. Both (2) positions, Fraud Prevention and Fraud Prevention and Ethics Management, have one thing in common: setting a Risk Management qualification as a requirement.

The researcher believes that the relevant qualifications for the position of Data Analyst as advertised by the National Prosecuting Authority (NPA) supposed to be amongst others Data and/ or Physical Science, Data Analysis and/ or Bachelor's Degree or equivalent (relevant) qualification (with Computer Science, Computer Auditing, Information Systems, Internal Audit, Data Science as major modules/ subjects) rather than Advance Diploma (NQF level 7)/ B-Tech in Policing, Law, Forensics as stipulated in the advert.

Turning to the three (3) Assistant Directors' posts of Forensic Auditor/ Investigations analysed and presented above, the researcher established that the number of years of experience and qualifications listed as requirements are not aligned, including that the posts are not titled the same way, in spite that the shortlisted and preferred candidates will be performing nearly the same duties of conducting investigations and/ or forensic audit of the reported fraud, corruption, irregularities, maladministration and financial misconduct by the approved methodology within their respective Departments. Moreover, it was established that these posts are graded and evaluated on the same level and advertised by three government institutions accountable to the DPSA. The two (2) positions titled Forensic Audit and Forensic Investigations set a Law as a qualification requirement. From the qualifications presented, the Office of Chief Justice referred to criminal and fraud investigations as qualifications, despite the fact that these might be referred to as modules in some institutions of higher learning in South Africa.

Table 4. Entry Level (Investigators) Posts

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Employment and Labour
Post/ Position	SENIOR FRAUD INVESTIGATOR: RISK
Required	✓ Interested candidates must have a three (3) year tertiary qualification in Accounting, Forensic Investigation, Internal Audit,

	Law, Policing, Risk Management, Risk and Security Management and CFE. Candidates must have a valid driving license plus two (2) years of functional experience in Anti-fraud and Corruption.
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[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 10 of 2023]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Office of the Chief Justice
Post/ Position	FORENSIC AUDITOR
Prerequisite	✓ Applicants must have a Grade 12 and three (3) year National Diploma or Bachelor's Degree (NQF level 6 & 7) in Accounting, Auditing, Criminal or Fraud Investigations, Law or Police Administration or any similar qualification. Applicants must have at least one (1) year of appropriate experience in the Forensic Auditing or Investigations field. Applicants are required to have an "advanced knowledge in financial investigations including the capability to apply knowledge in practical situations."

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 09 of 2022]

Department/ Institution/ Municipality	Department of Agriculture, Land Reform and Rural Development
Post/ Position	FORENSIC INVESTIGATOR
Set Criteria	✓ Candidates must have a Matric (Grade 12) Certificate and National Diploma in Accounting, Auditing, Forensic Investigations, Law and Policing. Candidates must have at least two (2) years of work experience in forensic investigations. Candidates must also have Forensic Investigations knowledge of tools (software/s), methodology and procedures applied, including being familiar with ACFE Professional Standards.

[Source: **DPSA**, Circular 26 of 2023]

For the entry-level Senior Fraud Investigator: Risk and Forensic Investigator, the researcher they have discovered that the two (2) vacancies shared the same number of years of experience, including Accounting/ Forensic Investigation(s)/ Internal Audit or Auditing/ Law and Policing as the required qualifications. One (1) vacancy set "a minimum of one (1) year relevant experience in forensic auditing/ investigations", although it shared the same qualifications to be specific Auditing, Accounting, Law or Police Administration with the other two (2) vacancies mentioned above. The researcher also found that the titles of the three (3) Fraud, Forensic Auditor/ Investigator positions are not named the same, despite that they perform the same role of conducting investigations. All three (3) entry-level vacancies share one thing in common, which is to set the Law qualification as a requirement.

In a nutshell, of the 24 vacancies presented and analysed, the Bachelor of Laws was set as a requirement for 15 advertised vacancies. The dominance of LLB qualifications in most of the careers was demonstrated by the University of Cape Town (UCT) (2023:64-65). The UCT emphasise that candidates who studied the Law. This is because, in South Africa, the LLB is regarded as "the

universal general qualification for the practice of the law." In layman's terms, the UCT expressed that individuals with a Law Degree "can be found across the whole business spectrum, from small firms to large corporations. They are legal advisors in tax, real estate, labour relations, contracts, public information, and acquisitions, forensic auditors and ombudsmen, ethics and employment officers, and policy and legislative analysts." Most publishing companies or organisations recruit LLB holders to be their legal editors, researchers, and writers.

Moreover, the UCT (2023:66) expressed that LLB holders are found in all sectors and spheres of the government in South Africa. They are employed as Prosecutors, Magistrates, Judges, Administrators, Legal Advisors, Lawyers, Legislation and Policy developers, State Advocates/ Attorneys, Law Researchers, Secretariat, Forensic Investigators and/ or Auditors, Quality Assurances Personnel, Inspectors, Project Managers, Registrars, Property Managers, Specialist: Compliance, etc. In a nutshell, LLB holders play a critical role across all government spheres, including their business spectrum.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that the DPSA as the custodian of public administration, grading and evaluation of the job descriptions as well as advertising vacancies of the government departments, must adequately align the job descriptions and requirements of Detectives, Forensic/ Fraud Investigators; Forensic Auditors; Ethics Officers; Fraud Prevention Officers; Anti-Fraud and Corruption Officers positions with the qualifications offered by the South African Universities and Colleges including regulatory bodies such as Association of Certified Fraud Examiners (ACFE), Institution of Commercial Forensic Practitioners (ICFP) and International Institute Of Certified Forensic Investigation (IICFIP). A similar recommendation must be extended to the South African Local Government Association (SALGA) as a regulatory body for local governments (municipalities) and the private sector to align their advert to universities, colleges, and regulatory bodies offering qualifications. The researcher believes that this will help the government departments, municipalities, state institutions and private sector to close the gap of the inconsistency of qualifications with the vacancies discovered, as on their current form, they disadvantage many graduates holding relevant qualifications in the field of forensic investigations, fraud prevention and/ or anti-fraud and corruption with career opportunities. It is further recommended that the most suitable and aligned qualifications for Detectives, Forensic/ Fraud Investigators, Forensic Auditors Ethics Officers, Fraud Prevention Officers, Anti-Fraud and Corruption Officers are a National or Advanced Diploma in Policing, Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice, Bachelor of Arts (Criminology and Psychology stream), Bachelor of Arts in Police Science, Bachelor of Arts (BA) in Public Governance with Policing Practice, Bachelor of Arts in Forensic Science and Technology, Bachelor of Laws and Bachelor of Social Science (Criminology), Higher Certificate in Criminal Justice and Forensic Investigations, Bachelor of Law (LLB), Postgraduate Diploma in Investigation and Forensic Accounting, Postgraduate Diploma in Forensic Auditing, Postgraduate Diplomas in Forensic Investigations and Criminal Justice and MPhil in Fraud Risk Management, perhaps Internal Audit, Accounting and Bachelor of Commerce.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper provided an overview of the inconsistency of academic qualifications, years of experience, and positions for forensic investigations job opportunities in the public sector of South Africa, despite the fact that most of the vacancies are graded and evaluated at the same level. Such inconsistency was demonstrated when two Assistant Directors' posts for Fraud Prevention and Anti-Fraud and Corruption were graded on the same level and advertised by the sole Department of Employment and Labour with different requirements of qualifications and years of experience. The study reveals that some of the qualifications mentioned in the advert are modules rather than the qualifications itself; for instance, Accounting, Forensics and Auditing tend to be modules for certain qualifications (e.g., Accounting and Auditing are modules for B Com in Accounting and Auditing at the University of Zululand (UNIZULU, 2023)). This paper emphasises that the relevant qualifications, amongst others to be set as a requirement for Forensic/ Fraud Investigators, Forensic Auditors; Ethics Officers, Fraud Prevention Officers, Anti-Fraud and Corruption Officers, and Detectives careers are National or advanced Diploma in Policing, Bachelor of Arts in Criminal Justice, Bachelor of Arts (Criminology and Psychology stream), Bachelor of Arts in Police Science, Bachelor of Arts (BA) in Public Governance with Policing Practice, Bachelor of Arts in Forensic Science and Technology, Bachelor of Laws and Bachelor of Social Science (Criminology), Higher Certificate in Criminal Justice and Forensic Investigations, Bachelor of Law (LLB), Postgraduate Diploma in Investigation and Forensic Accounting, Postgraduate Diploma in Forensic Auditing, Postgraduate Diplomas in Forensic Investigations and Criminal Justice and MPhil in Fraud Risk Management. Moreover, the study emphasises that candidates with the Bachelor of Arts (Law) and/ or LLB qualification have extensive career opportunities to grab as the qualification is set as a requirement in mostly advertised vacancies across the sectors and spheres of the government in South Africa.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

At present, conflict of interest is not applicable.

CONTRIBUTION OF AUTHOR

Tumiso Mokhomole is the article's principal author, a scholar with a Doctoral Degree and a seasoned Forensic Investigator.

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